

Polarographic study on parathion in micellar media

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Direct current polarographic study of parathion shows two reduction waves at pH 3.0–10.0. The second wave does not appear in highly alkaline medium due to the stable nature of hydroxylamine. Two waves also appear at pH 3.0–10.0 in presence of anionic surfactant, sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) as well as nonionic surfactant, Triton X-100. Half wave potential increases with increasing concentration of SDS while it decreases with increasing concentration of Triton X-100. The second reduction wave does not appear even at pH 3.0–10.0 in presence in cationic surfactant, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB). Half wave potential increases slightly with increasing concentration of CTAB.

Several chemicals¹ are being used to control pests in agriculture, public health, forestry, veterinary practices. Organophosphates are widely used as broad spectrum insecticides, acaricides, fumigants and nematicides. Organophosphates are non-systemic pesticides which contact stomach and respiratory action (cholinesterase inhibitor). Thus chemical crop protection is a profit induced poisoning process which affects our lives and economy. The migration of pesticides into various compartments of environment has generated public awareness concerning their fate and toxic effects. It is known that the surfactant is one of the important additives used in pesticides formulations, in order (i) to increase the solubility of the pesticide in aqueous medium, (ii) to stabilize the pesticide by controlling evaporation or decomposition (above CMC), (iii) to enhance the effectiveness of the pesticide by providing the fine spray (lower CMC) and (iv) studies in micellar media are helpful in exploring the mode of action of pesticides (redox behaviour) in biomacromolecular ensembles, (e.g. enzymes).

Amongst analytical methods used for pesticides, polarography has been found to be more sensitive, selective and reproducible. A good polarogram is obtained for pesticides containing an oxidisable or reducible group such as nitro, halogen, carbonyl etc. Pesticides not containing such a group can usually be determined by formation of a suitable derivatives. A few recently reported papers on this subject are summarized in the following paragraphs. Therefore there is a genuine interest in electrochemical studies of pesticide in micellar media.

Garcia *et al.*² have reported a polarographic study of the organochlorine pesticides, dieldrin, endosulfan and endosulfan sulphate in micellar solution. The best analytical signal to noise ratio was found in a mixture of Hyamine 2389 and Triton X-405 at pH 6. The pesticides can be determined in micellar solution by differential pulse polarography (DPP) using pulse amplitude, ΔE of -50 mV, over the range 1.0×10^{-6} mol L⁻¹ simultaneous analysis was based on hydrolysis of endosulfan and endosulfan sulphate in basic medium. Galvez *et al.*³ have reported a polarographic study of the reduction of herbicide, simazine, in solution of an anionic surfactants, sodium pentane sulphonate. In this case two reduction peaks were observed in differential pulse polarography (DPP) below pH 2.0. Whereas only one peak was obtained above pH 2.0. DP polarogram of simazine in oil water emulsion showed only one peak even at pH less than 2.0, suggesting that the pesticide hydrolysis was hindered in the emulsified medium. The limiting current in diffusion controlled and the electrode process was irreversible. The diffusion coefficient of simazine in emulsified medium is 8.85×10^{-6} cm² s⁻¹ and αn_i and K_f^0 (defined later) are 0.82 and 8.03×10^{-14} cm s⁻¹ respectively. Simazine was determined in a spiked irrigation water over the concentration range 8.0×10^{-7} – 4.0×10^{-5} . The limit of detection was 2.2×10^{-7} mol L⁻¹. Tandon *et al.*⁴ have reported two well defined diffusion controlled waves of dichloro diphenyl dichloroethane (DDD) and benzene hexachloride (BHC) at pH 7 in micellar medium. However polarographic studies have not been reported on parathion in micellar media.

Therefore, it was thought to be worth while to make po-

Fig. 1. Typical polarogram of parathion (1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3}) in acetate buffer at 25°C .

larographic study of parathion in micellar medium. The results obtained are described in this paper.

Results and discussion

A typical polarogram (Fig. 1) of using acetate buffer (pH 4.8) gives two reduction waves with $E_{1/2}$ value at -0.657 V and -0.94 V. The reduction was of diffusion controlled in nature. It was confirmed by studying the height of reduction wave at varying height of mercury column (h) over the orifice of capillary. For the logarithmic analysis of the wave, the following equation was used and E_{de} was plotted against $\log [i/(i_d - i)]$

$$E_{de} = \frac{0.0591}{\alpha n_a} \log \left(\frac{1.349 k_{f,h} t^{1/2}}{D_0^{1/2}} \right) - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$$

where, α = transfer coefficient, n_a = number of electron involved in reduction process, $k_{f,h}^0$ = potential dependent heterogeneous rate constant, t = drop time, D_0 = diffusion coefficient of electroactive substance, i = current and i_d = diffusion current.

The first term on the right hand side of this equation is equal to $E_{1/2}$ and the above equation can be written as

$$E_{de} = E_{1/2} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$$

The plot of E_{de} vs $\log [i/(i_d - i)]$ gave straight lines (Fig. 2) with slope 0.015 and 0.014 and intercepts at -0.657 V and -0.964 V. The first wave appears due to 4-electron reduction of nitrogroup of parathion into hydroxylamine and the second wave appear due to 2-electron reduction of hydroxylamine to amine. The following is the mechanism of successive reduction at dme (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The difference in the value of $E_{3/4}$ and $E_{1/4}$ attributes to the irreversibility of the reduction of parathion in buffer and micellar media. The difference in $E_{3/4}$ and $E_{1/4}$ is larger than the theoretical value expected for 4-electron and 2-electron reversible reduction. The irreversibility was also confirmed by studying the dependence of current on h_{corr} at different state of the wave. The current was independent of h_{corr} at the foot of the wave, whereas it was proportional to $h_{corr}^{1/2}$ at the plateau of the wave.

Effect of surfactants :

Fig. 3 shows the effect of varying concentration of Triton X-100 (1×10^{-2} – 5×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3}) at constant concentration of parathion (1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3}) and pH 4.8. It shows that the value of half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) for both waves decreases with increasing concentration of Triton X-100. Fig. 3 shows the effect of varying concentration of SDS (1×10^{-2} – 5×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3}) at constant concentration of parathion (1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3}) and pH 4.8. In this case $E_{1/2}$ increases sharply with increasing concentration of SDS. Fig. 3 shows the effect of varying concentration of CTAB (1×10^{-2} – 5×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3}) at constant concentra-

Fig. 2. Plot of E_{dc} vs $\log [i/(i_d - i)]$ for parathion (1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3}) in acetate buffer (pH 4.8) at 25°C .

tion of parathion (1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3}) and pH 4.8. In this case only one wave i.e. the first wave was obtained while the second wave disappeared completely. The $E_{1/2}$ of the first wave increases slightly with increasing concentration of CTAB.

The plot of E_{dc} vs $\log [i/(i_d - i)]$ was used to calculate the kinetic parameter αn_i and $k_{f,h}$ for each concentration of surfactants. A decrease in αn (3.7–3.3) was observed with the increase in concentration of ionic surfactants (SDS and CTAB). However, reversal was observed in case of non-ionic surfactants (TX-100). The decrease in α -value suggests that the irreversible reduction of parathion at dme becomes more difficult with increasing concentration of ionic surfactants while in the presence of TX-100 reduction of parathion is less difficult. The variation in the value of $k_{f,h}$ exhibits irreversible reduction of parathion in presence of TX-100 and difficult in ionic surfactants.

The above mentioned effect of the surfactant on the electrochemical nature of parathion is either due to the adsorption of the molecule at the electrode surface prior to reduction or due to decrease in the rate of electron transfer caused by the adsorption of the surfactant.

Effect of pH :

The reduction behaviour of parathion was studied at pH 3.0–12.0. The concentrations of parathion (1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3}), surfactants (1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3}) and potassium nitrate (1×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3}) were kept constant, pH was adjusted by adding NaOH and HCl solutions. Two waves were found in the presence of Triton X-100 at pH range 3.0–10.0 while only first wave was found at pH 10.40–12.00. The half wave potential of the first wave increases with increasing pH 3.0–10.0 and then it remains constant in the pH range 10.40–12.00. Similar behaviour was also observed on adding SDS. In presence of CTAB, only the first wave was obtained at pH 3.0–12.0 and its $E_{1/2}$ increases sharply with increasing pH.

The aforesaid results show that in acidic or mild basic medium (pH 3.0–10.0) parathion reduces to hydroxylamine and then to amine so two waves appear and in basic medium (pH 10.40–12.00) hydroxylamine is quite stable or does not reduce to amine so only the first wave appears. These findings are in line with the following results reported in the literature.

Fig. 3. Plot of [surfactant] vs $E_{1/2}$ for parathion (1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3}) and at pH 4.8.

DP polarographic studies³ on simazine show that the high concentration (>0.01%) of cationic and non-ionic surfactants suppressed the peak in the entire pH range. While the anionic surfactants exhibited different behaviour. DC polarography of pesticides⁶ containing azomethine showed that non-ionic surfactants suppressed the main wave. A mixture of Hyamine 2389 and Triton X-405 gave the best analytical signal-to-noise ratio for dieldrin, endosulfan and endosulfan sulphate by DP polarography². The increasing concentration of surfactants increased the irreversible electrode reactions of DDD and BHC⁴. DC polarography⁷ of pyrazoline-5-ones has shown that i_d of the second wave increased and i_d of the first wave gradually decreased with increasing concentration of surfactants.

Conclusion : The above results show that the polarography can be used successfully for routine analysis and identification of parathion in micellar media.

Experimental

Apparatus : Polarograph (264A) and omnigraphic X-Y recorder (RE 0089), dropping mercury electrode, platinum electrode and calomel electrode (KCl saturated) from Princeton USA, and Elico pH meter (LI-120, Hyderabad, India), were used.

Chemicals : Ethyl parathion (50%) (Bayer, India Ltd.),

acetic acid and sodium hydroxide (E. Merck, India), Triton X-100 and sodium dodecyl sulphate (Fluka, India). All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of solutions : Solution of ethyl parathion (0.01 M) was prepared in 50% aqueous methanol. Acetate buffer was prepared as usual⁵. Solution of potassium nitrate (0.1 M), hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide (0.01 M), cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, Triton X-100 and sodium dodecyl sulphate (0.1 M) were prepared in doubly distilled water (DW).

Procedure : Acetate buffer or sodium hydroxide solution or diluted hydrochloric acid, ethyl parathion solution and surfactant were placed in a cell, which was thermostated at 25°C. The total volume of the solution was made up to 10 ml. The inert atmosphere was ensured by passing nitrogen gas (purified after bubbling through alkaline pyrogallol solution) through the solution for about 10 min, and then the corresponding polarograms were recorded between 0.0 to -1.5 V with a pulse amplitude of 50 mV and a scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹.

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